

ISic1313

I.Sicily inscription 1313

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 301

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Μαρκία

2. Λουκιλία

3. χρηστὰ καὶ ἄ

4. μεμτος · αἰζωσ(εν)

5. ἔτια εἴκοσι

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Markia Loukilia, honest and good. Lived for 20 years.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492918

EDCS 39101683

PHI 140805

PHI 316229

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0490 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 108

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5714

Bechtel, F., Collitz, H., Meister, R. C., Bezenberger, A. 1884-1915. Sammlung der griechischen Dialekt-Inschriften. Göttingen. At 5238

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